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Analysis of hospital culture on patient safety concerns among nursing staff in an accredited hospital

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Abstract

Introduction: Culture refers to shared values and beliefs that interact with a systems structure and control mechanisms to produce behavioral norms. It influences patient safety directly by determining accepted practices and indirectly by acting as a barrier or enabler to the adoption of behaviors that promote patient safety. Understanding the components and influencers of culture and assessing the safety culture is essential to developing strategies that creates a culture committed to providing the safest possible care for the patients

Aim: Analysis of hospital culture on patient safety concerns among nursing staffs in an accredited hospital, Mangalore.

Objectives:

- To assess the current knowledge of hospital culture on patient safety among nursing staffs.
- To study the prevalent or existing patient safety cultures and concerns in an accredited hospitals.

Methodology

- Design: survey among nursing staffs in an accredited hospital. [a descriptive study]
- Sample size: 200 nursing staffs from an accredited hospital in Mangalore.
- Area of the study: An accredited hospital in Mangalore.
- Tool: questionnaire.

Result: The study mainly focuses among the nursing staff. Through the study, it was found that majority of nursing staff are aware regarding the patient safety goals in hospital. Majority of the staffs were well known regarding the hospital culture and very few were unaware regarding the culture of the hospital.

Conclusion: The study result can be used for the betterment of hospital safety culture practiced and used among nursing staffs in all the hospital and health care delivery systems and also to study the awareness of patient safety cultures and practices among the nursing staffs in the hospitals.

Keywords: awareness, culture, nursing, patient, safety

Introduction

Safety culture is the gathering of the ideals, perceptions and values that personnel percentage when it comes to risks within an business enterprise, along with a administrative center or network. Safety culture is a part of organizational way of life, and has been defined in a ramification of ways; appreciably the countrywide academies of technology and the affiliation of land grant and public universities have published summaries in this topic in 2014 and 2016. The protection culture of an company and its safety management system are closely related, however the relationship isn't clearly that the protection way of life complies with the formal protection management machine the safety tradition of an agency can't be created or modified overnight; it develops through the years because of history, work environment, the team of workers, fitness and safety practices, and control leadership: "companies, like organisms, adapt. An agency's protection tradition is in the end meditated inside the manner safety is addressed in its workplaces (whether boardroom or shop floor). In fact an organisation's safety control gadget is not a set of guidelines and tactics on a bookshelf, however how the ones rules and methods are carried out into the place of business, that allows you to be motivated via the protection tradition of the corporation or place of business. Whilst defining safety way of life some authors recognition on attitudes, where others see safety tradition being expressed via behaviors and sports. The protection tradition of an company can be a vital influence on human performance in protection-associated responsibilities and consequently on the protection overall performance of the

agency. Many proprietary and educational methods claim to evaluate protection culture, but few had been confirmed towards actual protection performance. The considerable majority of surveys examine key troubles together with management, involvement, commitment, communicate, and incident reporting. Some safety culture maturity tools are utilized in consciousness institution sports, although few of these (even the most famous) were tested towards corporation incident quotes. International Patient Safety Goals (IPSG) help accredited organizations address specific areas of concern in some of the most problematic areas of patient safety.

- Goal 1: Identify patients correctly
- Goal 2: Improve effective communication
- Goal 3: Improve the safety of high-alert medications
- Goal 4: Ensure safe surgery
- Goal 5: Reduce the risk of health care-associated infections
- Goal 6: Reduce the risk of patient harm resulting from falls

In a have a look at at the present day kingdom of patient protection way of life in lebanese hospitals: a look at at baseline. The goal of the observe is to conduct a baseline evaluation of patient safety subculture in lebanese hospitals. The study followed a pass- sectional research design and applied the medical institution survey on patient safety culture. A complete of 6807 hospital personnel participated in the examine along with hospital-employed physicians, nurses, scientific and non-clinical staffs and others. Survey respondents were primarily employed in medical and surgical units. The scale with the highest wonderful ratings were teamwork inside units, health center management aid for patient safety, and organizational gaining knowledge of and non-stop development, while with the lowest rankings covered staffing's and non-punitive response to blunders. Bivariate and multivariate evaluation revealed significant differences throughout hospitals of various size and accreditation popularity. Study findings provide evidence that can be utilized by coverage makers, managers and leaders who're able to create the lifestyle and commitment had to discover and remedy underlying systemic reasons related to affected person safety [1].

in every other study on assessment of patient protection subculture in saudi arabian hospitals. Healthcare businesses in saudi arabia are striving to improve patient safetyman quality care via implementation of safety machine and growing a way of life of safety. The motive of this observe is to evaluate the extent to which the culture helps patient safety at saudi hospitals' surveyed questionnaire turned into allotted sanatorium-wide in thirteen trendy hospitals in riyadh city., to 223 fitness professionals along with nurses, technicians, managers and clinical body of workers. Normal affected person protection became rated terrific or very good through 60% of respondents, perfect via 33% and failing or terrible by 7%. More than half of the respondents thought that managers forget about safety issues that take place time and again. The look at concluded that management is a crucial element to the effectiveness of patient safety tasks

and reaction to errors is an critical determinant of protection lifestyle in healthcare organizations [2].

patient protection and satisfactory development of fitness care transport to the sufferers are a number of the maximum priorities of healthcare system. The objective of the examine turned into to determine the know-how of patient protection amongst postgraduates and nurses in a tertiary care clinic. The take a look at was carried out among the postgraduate citizens and nurses operating at the pediatric hospital lahore. Each post graduates and nurses have been asked to finish questionnaire about patient protection. A total of 150 residents and a hundred and fifty nurses had been protected. The scores of each postgraduate residents and nurses had been comparable in all domains having definitely worded questions with insignificant difference in imply score. Each postgraduate citizens and nurses showed high-quality mindset with appropriate understanding and belief closer to patient safety [3].

pass sectional surveys among nurses and sufferers were executed in standard acute care hospitals, eu hospitals and us hospitals. The proportion of nurses reporting negative of truthful excellent of affected person care various subtle by way of u. S. A. (from eleven% to 47%) as did quotes for nurses who gave their health center a poor are falling safety grade (4% to 18%). This look at derives that patients in hospitals with better paintings environments were much more likely to price the medical institution notably and recommended their hospitals, whereas people with better ratios of affected person to nurses were less probable to price them highly. Nurses and patients agreed on which hospitals supplied true care and may be encouraged. Deficits in health facility care first-rate have been commonplace in all nations. Improvement of health facility paintings environments might be a tremendously lowcost approach to enhance safety and pleasant in health facility care to boom affected person satisfaction [4].

Methodology

The research approach adopted in this study was a descriptive study; it includes collection of information through questionnaire.

Method of Collection of Data

It includes collection of information, opinions and attitude directly from the samples using a structured questionnaire.

Source of Data

The primary data was collected from the staff nurses of selected hospital through a direct structured questionnaire.

Sample and Sampling Technique: Sample size of the study was 200 staff nurses, Simple random sampling technique was adopted to select the nurses.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: knowledge regarding IPSG

Variables	Yes	No
Knowledge regarding IPSG goals	200	0

Fig 1: indicating knowledge regarding IPSPG

This figure reveals that 100% were aware of the international patient safety goals (IPSPG).

Awareness of Patient Safety Cultures

Table 2: awareness of patient safety cultures in the hospital

Variables	Yes	No
Awareness of patient safety cultures in the hospital	158	42

Fig 2: indicates awareness of patient safety cultures in the hospital

- Out of 200 samples 79% samples are aware of the patient safety cultures in the hospital.

Patient Safety Incidences

Table 3: patient safety incidents occurred in the departments

Variables	Yes	No
Patient safety incidents occurred in the departments	8	192

Fig 3: indicates patient safety incidents occurred in the departments

- Out of 200 samples, incidences related patient safety has occurred in 4% sample's departments.

Identification of The Patient

Table 4: mode of identification of the patient

Variables	a	b	C
Mode of identification of the patients	136	48	16

Fig 4: indicates mode of identification of the patients

- Out of 200 samples 68% samples are using ID bands to identify the patients, 24% samples are calling out the patient name to identify the patient and 8% samples used the bed numbers for the identification of the patients.

Handling of Emergency Medicines

Table 5: shows handling of high alert medicines in the departments

Variables	YES	NO
Handling of emergency medicines in the departments	200	0

Fig 5: indicates handling of high alert medicines in the departments.

- 100% of samples are in contact and dealing with emergency medicines

Table 6: shows storage of high alert medicines in the departments

Variables	a	b	C
Storage of high alert medicines in the departments	180	0	20

Fig 6: indicates the storage of high alert medicines in the departments

- Out of 200 samples 90% samples are stored the high alert medicines with high alert labelled on it 10% samples are storing the high alert medicines in the nurses station

Identification of Fall Risk Patients

Table 7: shows identification of fall risk patients in the departments

Variables	a	b	C
Identification of fall risk patients in the departments	104	10	86

Fig 7: indicates identification of fall risk patients in the departments

- Out of 200 samples 52% samples are prefer to identify fall risk patients by their disease condition
- 5% samples were prefer to identify fall risk patients by fall risk assessment record
- 43% samples preferred to identify fall risk patients by observation.

Result

It turned into discovered that majority of nursing body of workers had been conscious concerning the affected person safety goals in sanatorium. Majority of the staffs are widely known concerning the clinic subculture and very few are unaware concerning the lifestyle of the medical institution. The incidences happened associated with sufferers are mentioned to manager and are also raised on line in step with the sanatorium policy. Majority of team of workers nurses uses identity bands to pick out the patients while few group of workers nurses uses patient name and mattress quantity to discover the patients of their branch. In this look at all of the respondents were aware concerning the high alert medicines, out of which majority high alert medicinal drugs had been saved with label in separate region and few had been saved in nurse's station. All of the respondents had been privy to the pre- and submit-surgical checklists. All of the samples have been a hit in communicating records's concerning surgical operation to sufferers on time, and privy to the hic regulations inside the clinic. For the duration of the observe most of the respondents did no longer witness clinic acquired contamination however few respondents did. Majority of the respondents preferred to perceive fall risk patients by way of their disease circumstance, few preferred to discover fall hazard sufferers via fall threat assessment document and few desired to become aware of fall chance sufferers with the aid of statement.

Discussion

A comparable study aimed to decide the attention level of the nursing staffs for policies and processes related to first-class of care, patient protection and trendy protection and investigate the congruence of understanding inside implementation. Key informant interviews had been performed on 85 nurses in a tertiary healthcare facility and implementation statics on choose exceptional and patient protection signs were obtained from clinical audit programme. The attention level of the nurses on great,

affected person safety and preferred safety turned into located to be good. The compliance on high-quality and patient safety signs turned into observed decrease than the knowledge stage. The take a look at concluded that the demanding situations of remodeling knowledge to affected person care practices want to take account of labor environment determinants⁵. Healthcare agencies have become aware of the importance of reworking organizational tradition so that it will improve patient safety. Growing interest in protection subculture has been followed through the evaluation tools focused on the cultural thing of affected person protection improvement efforts. This paper discusses the usage of safety tradition assessment as a device for improving affected person safety. It describes the traits of cultural evaluation tools presently available and discuss their present day and capacity use, which include brief examples from healthcare corporations that have undertaken such assessments. The paper additionally highlights essential processes that healthcare groups need to recall whilst finding out to apply the equipment^[6].

as the discharge of institute of medication reviews within the U. S. A. Of the USA, extensive interest has arisen in studying affected person protection culture; but, the concept stays poorly described. A concept evaluation based on caron and bowers' approach turned into finished using 45 papers, three books and 3 theses after examination of the abstracts to perceive definitions, dimensions, views and results wished for content material and dimensional analyses. Nurses' shared values, beliefs and behavioural norms in the direction of affected person protection have been recognized because the overarching dimensions of the patient protection culture. The 4 sub-dimensions of patient safety lifestyle have been synthesized as device, non-public, project-associated and interplay. Two principal philosophical perspectives, functional and interpretative, have been brought to the analysis and in addition rationalization become furnished. It's miles predicted that understanding the character, in addition to the important thing factors of the idea, could assist with analysing the prevailing protection way of life and assist to decide the techniques to construct or shape the protection subculture^[7].

Conclusion

Overall to conclude in this study, the study result can be used for the betterment of hospital safety culture practiced and used among nursing staffs in all the hospital and health care delivery systems and also to study the awareness of patient safety cultures and practices among the nursing staffs in the hospitals.

Recommendations

Structured training program with defined pre and post tests can improve the effectiveness of the patient safety trainings to all sections of staff. Also, table-top exercises could be planned for the trainings through more effective trainers can help to improve the awareness of patient safety culture among all groups of staff.

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